

THE ROLE OF EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY IN ENSURING THE QUALITY OF STUDENT LEARNING

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Abstract: This article discusses the teacher factor as one of the most crucial elements in achieving high quality in education and training qualified personnel. It emphasizes the importance of teachers' knowledge level and professional skills. The article also addresses the need to familiarize teachers with modern teaching technologies that meet contemporary requirements and to develop skills and competencies that ensure their effective use.

Key words: education, development, method, technology, technological process, pedagogical technology, teaching technology, pedagogical process.

The social changes taking place in society in recent years, the interpretation of the issue of training mature personnel who meet the requirements of the time as one of the most important factors influencing the further development of our society, require serious changes in the educational process. However, all the reforms being implemented in our country are aimed at human perfection, well-being, their interests, and most importantly, raising a harmoniously developed generation.[1.175]

Scientific and technological progress necessitates the introduction of new technologies not only in numerous branches of production but also in the cultural sphere and the domain of social and humanitarian knowledge. Consequently, one of the pressing issues of today is pedagogical technology.[1.280]

The process of integration with the global community has created opportunities to utilize new teaching technologies and rich experience from abroad in education. Furthermore, at present, it is imperative to harness the achievements of science and technology, particularly the advances made in linguistics, pedagogy, didactics, and psychology, to enhance the effectiveness of the educational process.

Currently, one of the most crucial issues in education is the implementation of educational objectives based on the goals, content, methods, tools, organizational forms of teaching, and the material of the subject being studied in the learning process.

It is well known that higher education is one of the most important links in continuous education, as it plays a vital role in training well-rounded, knowledgeable, and skilled personnel for various sectors of the national economy.

In achieving high quality in education and training qualified personnel, the teacher factor, their level of knowledge, and professional skills are among the most crucial elements. When preparing personnel in higher education, it is necessary to focus on two important aspects: 1. Professional training of the future specialist.

2. Their pedagogical preparedness.

For the first aspect, it is essential to determine the purpose and content of teaching, i.e., what to teach, while for the second, it is important to address issues related to teaching methods, i.e., how to teach. In methodological literature, one can encounter a wide variety of

terms associated with the word "technology": pedagogical technology, technical technology, educational technology, new technology, modern technology, humanitarian technology, and so on.[2.203]

When discussing this, it is first necessary to separately consider three types of technology: technical technology, educational technology, and teaching technology. Technology originally entered the educational process from production. In production, the terms "technological process," "technological operation," "technological map," and "technological regime" are widely used. In particular, technology is a production process, and pedagogical technology is a new pedagogical process.

Currently widely used pedagogical technology is actually derived from the English word "Educational technology," which means educational technology. Pedagogical technology is used, including technologies that shape the personality, develop its qualities and characteristics, and technologies related to teaching and learning, i.e., didactic technologies. The main feature of an educational technologist is design, implementation, guaranteed result. When applying pedagogical technologies, a guaranteed result can be achieved, since the student is at the center of learning. This process can be applied in general pedagogical, specific methodological, and modular directions. [2.256]

However, in our opinion, it would be correct to consider it expedient to use a differentiated approach in addition to these concepts in teaching foreign languages to students. Pedagogical technology involves a system more related to upbringing, while teaching technology includes operations with teaching educational material. Since the educational process is understood as a whole and interconnected, pedagogical technology is considered as a system representing the integrity of the technologization of the educational process.

When we talk about the use of new modern technologies in teaching foreign languages, we believe that it is advisable to consider teaching, i.e., educational technology, separately, since educational technologies are understood as the organization of lessons, the search for and creation of effective methods of mastering knowledge, taking into account human internal resources, cooperation in the process of optimizing forms of education. [2.305]

Teaching technology is also an integral part of educational technology, in which the goal of teaching is set more clearly, that is, it is a process that ensures the guaranteed achievement of the result, intended and defined through didactic actions performed in a certain sequence, aimed at achieving a goal related to a specific topic. It is reflected in the technological map. [3.226]

In general, this can be called a systematic approach to the design of the educational process. The famous didactic scientist Jan Amos Kamensky also dreamed of designing a teaching process that would live as accurately as a clock mechanism in his time. Modern teaching technology in foreign language teaching aims to form skills and abilities that ensure that foreign language teachers are aware of modern teaching technologies and effectively use them, meeting the requirements of the time at the present stage of society's development.

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